

INTELLIGENCE SHINES LIGHT IN THE DARKNESS

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Annotation: This article talks about Anbar Atin's treatise "Black Philosophy" and its educational value.

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In the second half of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century, there were significant positive changes and shifts in the cultural life of the Kokhan Khanate. During this period, new prose and poetic works were created in the works of poets and poetesses. In these works, valuable views on the state system, social problems of the time, ethical issues, and youth education are highlighted. It is no exaggeration to say that Anbar Otin, one of the poets who wrote in the Kokan literary environment, has a worthy place among such artists.

Despite the fact that Anbar Atin grew up in an ordinary Bozchi family, he was very devoted to science and poetry from childhood. Dilshad studied at the equestrian school and began to practice poetry independently. Already in school, he was familiar with the works of famous poets of his time. Later, with her sharp mind and talent, she gained respect among the women of the neighborhood and for some time was also engaged in teaching. The poetess, who followed Uvaisi more in her work, considered Navoi as her first teacher. He was well aware of the works of Muqumi, Furqat, and Zavqi. Anbar wrote mainly in two languages: Uzbek and Tajik. Despite being ill for many years, he continues to create. At the end of his life, he organized a devan. The poet's ghazals, poems, epics, poetic biography and treatises are included in Devon.

Anbar Atin's works are imbued with ideas of enlightenment and humanitarianism. He dreams of the people's happiness in the true sense, and at the same time he puts the people's interests above his own interests. He not only describes the injustice and spiritual poverty of his time, the hard life of the population, the hardships and sufferings of the people, but also shows a social reaction to them. Calls the masses to fight against injustice and oppression. In addition, as an enlightened poetess, she instills her moral views aimed at improving the spirituality of people into her works. In order to cultivate the

spiritual perfection of his homeland, to protect it from oppression and injustice, the penman, among his peers, fights valiantly to spread his knowledge of enlightenment throughout the Khanate. Anbar Atin's social views are widely reflected in his pamphlets together with his ghazals. It is important to note that in his treatises, he interprets ethical issues in a philosophical or metaphorical form and reveals the meaning. In particular, the treatise "Black Philosophy" ("Risoi ai falsafai siyohan") is one of the rare works not only in the work of Anbar Otin, but also in the history of Uzbek literature. Because in the work, the life of the ordinary people, together with their way of life, social problems of the time, various moral evils that are on the rise, the oppression of the colonizers, the sufferings of creative people and pen artists are under poetic observation.

The work "Black Philosophy" consists of an introduction and 4 chapters. In the introduction, the poet, who is faithful to the traditions of classical literature, mentions the reasons for writing the treatise. In the first chapter, the artist defines and describes his opinions about black happiness, black intention and black people: "There are black people, but they themselves are black, and the light of enlightenment fills them in their hearts and they spread their light to the world through eloquence and language masterpieces. For example, a black lamp, without oil and a candle holder, illuminates a snake's hut" [p. 1.84]

It can be seen that in the first season, the writer emphasizes social life and inequalities in the process of explaining the different meanings of the word black. That is, it emphasizes that the people who make the world alive with their black work are actually innocent, like white light, and on the contrary, it emphasizes how ugly and black the actions of white-skinned and white-armed people are. However, a perceptive person can observe purity and the meaning of the universe in the form of an Abyssinian. Anbar, who has gathered the qualities of courage, enthusiasm, and goodness in the image of black people, admits that whites who have wealth do not have any qualities of blacks. With these thoughts, the poetess was able to interpret social inequality in her own way.

In the second chapter of the work, "The Difference", Anbar Otin mainly expresses his views on moral issues. In this season, the creator highlights the situation of women of that time, the situation of peers who could not show their talent as a result of various discriminations. The description of the immoral vices that are on the rise in the times, including the poor marriage of girls and young people, polygamy, and the bad attitude of nobles to female servants. These situations, in turn, show that the society is becoming unconscious, that the

freedom of women is limited, and how social injustices are taking root among the people.

"Alas, this time is a time of depravity and sorrow,
For some, it is a time of pleasure, for someone it is a time of pain.
Young life is wasted, but with confusion and sadness,
Gulchehra is not a gulag, Khori is a Mughal co-house" [Page 1.93]

It is not an exaggeration to say that the above opinions are a proof that not only the Kokan Khanate, but also the entire Turanian land, women are helpless and helpless, and on the contrary, men are turning into wild beasts with their immoral vices such as indulgence in sensuality. It is important that Anbar horse includes the most loving people in the world - mothers. The difference is that black people are good at beauty, but at the same time, they are handsome, handsome and pleasant, and it's no wonder that we are the children of such kind people.

Despite the injustice and immorality in the society, the poetess looks at the future with the eyes of hope. He expresses confidence that one day immorality in the society will be educated, women and girls will get rid of the obstacles to acquiring worldly knowledge and they will be respected among the people of knowledge for their work. In this era, all the oppressed people have a good life and live a peaceful life, so their generation will grow up to be patriotic, hospitable, and cheerful.[Page 1.94]

In the later chapters of the treatise, the views of the poetess will rise together with the process of education. Anbar Otin comments on the importance of labor education in the education of a person. After all, the fate of people who spent their whole lives in labor and hardship is an epic in languages. Our great-grandfather Alisher Navoi also preferred to work hard to overcome the ego. In the image of Farhad alone, he creates the image of a perfect person who has overcome his ego through hard work and has understood his dream in connection with the dream of the people. In accordance with the educational and moral thoughts of his teachers, Anbar Atin calls those who gain wealth by using the labor of others to spend their lives in pleasure, whether they are kings or officials, who are truly fortunate.

As the society becomes more and more unhappy, the country is plunged into darkness. Therefore, if everyone works with their own mind and follows moral standards, they will be able to eliminate not only the darkness that is covering the world, but also the evil. At the heart of the above-mentioned

thoughts of Anbar-Otin, there is definitely a call to the people to search for a way to fight against the Tsar's government and its policies with progressive people.

In short, Anbar is distinguished by the philosophy of horse creation. The treatise "Philosophy of the Blacks" has its place in our literature with its philosophical observations, wealth of socio-ethical views, rightness, and high culture. The fate of the people, political and social issues, moral standards are reflected in the end of the poet's work. Describes the important life problems of the time in a simple, fluent way. In this respect, the treatise "Black Philosophy" has not lost its spiritual and moral significance even today.

References:

1. .Anbar Otin – “Devon”. G’afur G’ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san’at nashriyoti. Toshkent – 1970
2. D.Yusupova - "O'zbek mumtoz adabiyoti tarixi". Toshkent. "Akademnashr" – 2013
3. <https://arxiv.uz>
4. [w.w.w.ziyouz.com](http://www.ziyouz.com) kutubxonasi
5. Abdurakhimov, Bobirjon Abdunabiyevich, et al. "A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO MANAGING THE HEALTH AND RISK FACTORS OF THEIR WORKERS." Academic research in educational sciences 4.2 (2023): 209-213.
6. Khaitov, Javokhir, Khusan Khakberdiev, and Aida Kamilova. "MUNG BEANS ARE A SOURCE OF PROTEIN AND A HIGH ENERGY SOURCE." International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research 2.12 (2022): 61-63.

